

A

RNAseq TSC vs controls			
Gene	Log2 (FC)	p-value	q-value
<i>CNTN1</i>	-0.43	1.8E-01	7.5E-01
<i>CNTN2</i>	0.49	1.4E-01	6.9E-01
<i>CNTN3</i>	-1.32	5.0E-05	4.4E-03
<i>CNTN4</i>	-0.44	1.8E-01	7.6E-01
<i>CNTN5</i>	-0.45	1.4E-01	7.0E-01
<i>CNTN6</i>	0.08	8.4E-01	1.0E+00

B

C

Supplementary Figure 1. (A) – RNAseq data indicating that *CNTN3* was the most significantly down-regulated gene of the contactin family (log2 fold change = -1.32, q-value = 0.004, n = 12 TSC vs n = 10 controls); (B) – Average immunoreactivity was lower in neuropil in cortical tubers compared to control; (E) – Average immunoreactivity for synaptophysin (SYP) was reduced in neuropil in cortical tubers; *p<0.01, Student's t-test